

ISic0285

I.Sicily inscription 0285

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

volcanic

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Aetna

Place of origin (modern)

Santa Maria di Licodia

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania, inventory 345

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Cura[tores---]
2. Q(uintus) Mac [ulnius---]
3. T(itus) Trut [tedius---]
4. A(ulus) Turiu[s A](uli) [OCHAC ---]

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

Curators Quintus Maculnius, Titus Truttedius, Aulus Turius, son of Aulus

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491495

EDR 139643

EDCS 22200385

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0285. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4334863>